

Performance and Emission Characteristics of Biodiesel-Blend in CRDI Diesel Engine – A Review

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ABSTRACT

The rising global demand for energy, coupled with the rapid depletion of fossil fuel resources, has intensified the search for clean and renewable alternatives. Among these, biodiesel has attracted considerable attention due to its renewable origin, biodegradability, and potential to reduce harmful exhaust emissions. This review paper examines the performance and emission behavior of biodiesel–diesel blends when used in Common Rail Direct Injection (CRDI) engines. With its ability to precisely regulate injection pressure and timing, CRDI technology is particularly effective in enhancing the combustion of biodiesel blends. The study highlights the influence of biodiesel feedstock, blending ratio, and injection parameters on key performance aspects such as Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE), Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC), and combustion characteristics. It also evaluates the effect of biodiesel blends on exhaust emissions, including nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), unburned hydrocarbons (HC), and particulate matter (PM). In addition, the role of fuel additives and nanotechnology in improving engine efficiency and reducing emissions is discussed. Overall, this review provides a comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges associated with biodiesel use in CRDI engines and identifies future research directions toward cleaner and more efficient diesel technologies.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Biodiesel blend, CRDI Diesel engine, Emission, Performance

INTRODUCTION

Energy is the driving force of modern civilization, powering industries, transportation, households, and global economic growth. At present, most of this demand is met through fossil fuels such as coal, petrol, and diesel. However, these resources are depleting rapidly while their excessive use continues to release harmful pollutants including carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbons (HC), and particulate matter (PM). Such emissions contribute to global warming, acid rain, air pollution, and severe health problems. This dual challenge of resource depletion and environmental degradation has created a pressing need for alternative, eco-friendly fuels. Biodiesel has emerged as one of the most promising substitutes for conventional diesel. Derived from renewable sources such as vegetable oils, non-edible oils, animal fats, and waste cooking oil, biodiesel is biodegradable, non-toxic, and capable of reducing harmful emissions. It is produced mainly through transesterification, where oils or fats react with

alcohol in the presence of a catalyst to yield fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) and glycerol. Since biodiesel shares many physical and chemical properties with diesel, it can be used in existing engines with little or no modification. However, certain differences—such as higher viscosity, lower calorific value, and greater oxygen content—can influence engine performance, combustion characteristics, and emission levels. Parallel to the development of biodiesel, advancements in diesel engine technology have introduced the Common Rail Direct Injection (CRDI) system, which provides precise control of injection timing, pressure, and quantity through electronically operated injectors. This technology enhances fuel atomization, improves combustion, and reduces emissions, making CRDI engines highly suitable for testing biodiesel blends. Recent studies have examined the use of biodiesel–diesel blends (such as B10, B20, etc.) in CRDI engines to evaluate their effect on performance parameters like Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE), Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC), and cylinder pressure, as well as emissions including CO, HC, NO_x, and smoke. Results indicate

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that biodiesel blends generally improve combustion efficiency and reduce CO, HC, and PM emissions due to their inherent oxygen content. However, a notable drawback is the increase in NO_x emissions, which is often attributed to higher in-cylinder combustion temperatures. Researchers are addressing this challenge through optimized injection strategies, blend ratios, exhaust gas recirculation (EGR), selective catalytic reduction (SCR), and the incorporation of fuel additives. In addition, nanotechnology and alcohol-based additives are being explored to enhance fuel properties, promote cleaner combustion, and reduce harmful exhaust gases. Feedstock selection also plays a key role in biodiesel performance, with options ranging from edible oils like soybean and palm oil to non-edible oils such as jatropha, karanja, and neem, as well as waste oils and animal fats. Each feedstock influences viscosity, energy content, and oxygen levels differently, leading to varied effects on engine behavior and emissions. Despite its advantages, biodiesel faces challenges such as higher production costs, fuel instability during storage, and cold-weather performance issues. Standardization of fuel properties and long-term engine durability are also concerning. Nevertheless, the integration of biodiesel with CRDI technology, along with the use of additives and improved processing methods, provides a promising path forward. This review consolidates research findings on biodiesel blends in CRDI diesel engines, with emphasis on performance, combustion behavior, and emission characteristics. It further explores the impact of additives, feedstocks, and injection parameters while identifying both the benefits and limitations of biodiesel use. By presenting current knowledge and future prospects, this study aims to support ongoing efforts toward cleaner, more efficient, and sustainable diesel engine technologies.

2. Characteristics of Biodiesel

Biodiesel, produced through the transesterification of vegetable oils, non-edible oils, animal fats, and waste cooking oils into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), has drawn significant interest as an alternative to petroleum diesel. Its fuel characteristics differ

considerably from conventional diesel, and these differences strongly influence engine performance, combustion efficiency, and exhaust emissions. Over the years, researchers have examined these variations in detail. Demirbas (2009) observed that the calorific value of biodiesel is lower than that of petroleum diesel, primarily due to its oxygenated molecular structure. This reduction in heating value leads to slightly higher brake specific fuel consumption when biodiesel is used in diesel engines. Supporting this, Oliveira and Da Silva (2013) reported calorific values in the range of 38–40 MJ/kg for biodiesels derived from different feedstocks, in contrast to about 46 MJ/kg for diesel. Sanjid et al. (2014) reached similar conclusions in their work on palm and jatropha biodiesel, noting that reduced heating value was the major factor behind increased fuel usage. Hoekman et al. (2012) added that although biodiesel has less energy per unit mass, the oxygen content present in the fuel enhances combustion efficiency, offsetting some of the energy loss. In agreement, Graboski and McCormick (1998) also linked biodiesel's lower energy density to marginal reductions in engine power output.

2.1 Density and Viscosity

The physical properties of density and viscosity have received considerable attention. Alptekin and Canakci (2008) showed that biodiesel blends are denser and more viscous than conventional diesel, which can negatively affect fuel spray and atomization. Lapuerta et al. (2008) confirmed this by demonstrating that higher viscosity results in larger droplet formation during injection, ultimately influencing the combustion process. Wan Ghazali et al. (2015) reported that increased viscosity contributed to poor cold-starting characteristics in diesel engines. Similarly, Silitonga et al. (2013) highlighted that viscosity issues could be mitigated by blending biodiesel with diesel to achieve better atomization. Arbab et al. (2013) further emphasized that modern injection technologies, particularly CRDI systems, can counterbalance these shortcomings through precise control of injection pressure. Fig.1 represents the density values of biodiesel blends.

Fig.1 Density values of biodiesel blends

Fig.2 Kinematic viscosity values of biodiesel blends

2.2 Cetane number

With respect to cetane number, biodiesel generally performs better than diesel. Knothe (2005) noted that higher cetane numbers shorten ignition delay and promote smoother combustion. Ryan and Knothe (2003) found typical cetane numbers for biodiesels to be in the range of 50–65, compared to 45–55 for petroleum diesel. Rizwanul Fattah et al. (2013) showed that higher cetane ratings improve ignition quality but may also contribute to elevated NO_x emissions due to higher peak combustion temperatures. Sharma and Singh (2009) similarly observed that while cetane-rich biodiesel enhances engine startability and combustion stability, the associated NO_x rise remains a challenge. Lapuerta et al. (2008) supported these findings, presenting

experimental evidence of reduced ignition delay when biodiesel blends were used. Fig.2 represents the kinematic viscosity values of biodiesel blends.

2.3 Flash point and Cold flow

Other fuel characteristics such as flash point and cold flow properties are also important. Pinto et al. (2005) reported that biodiesel generally has a much higher flash point than diesel—often above 120°C—making it safer to store and transport. Graboski and McCormick (1998) echoed this advantage, highlighting biodiesel's reduced flammability risk during handling. However, its poor cold flow properties are a limitation. Das and Agarwal (2001) showed that biodiesel tends to crystallize at low temperatures, which can cause operational problems

in cold climates. Jain and Sharma (2010) found that biodiesel usually exhibits higher cloud and pour points than diesel, restricting its suitability in winter conditions. Worgetter and Prankl (1996) emphasized that biodiesels with higher saturated fatty acid content, such as palm-based biodiesel, are more vulnerable to gelling at low temperatures. To counter this, Sanjid et al. (2014) recommended blending strategies to improve cold-weather performance.

2.4 Iodine value

The iodine value, a measure of unsaturation, is another property that has been extensively studied. Jain and Sharma (2010) reported that biodiesels with higher iodine values, such as soybean oil-based biodiesel, are more prone to oxidation, making them less stable during storage. Worgetter and Prankl (1996) confirmed this by showing that fuels with lower iodine values, like coconut biodiesel, are much more stable. Dunn and Knothe (2003) further demonstrated that high levels of unsaturation accelerate oxidative degradation. Likewise, Anwar et al. (2009) confirmed that biodiesels with high iodine numbers require antioxidants to maintain stability. Silitonga et al. (2013) also concluded that iodine value remains one of the most critical parameters for assessing biodiesel quality and long-term usability.

2.5 Metal contamination

Metal contamination in biodiesel has also been reported to influence fuel quality. Dunn and Knothe (2003) demonstrated that copper contamination, even in trace amounts, accelerates oxidation and reduces storage life. Anwar et al. (2009) observed similar issues, finding that metal ions catalyze degradation and lead to gum and deposit formation. Arbab et al. (2013) stressed the importance of monitoring metal content during biodiesel production. Silitonga et al. (2013) likewise highlighted that metals negatively affect stability, while Jain and Sharma (2010) suggested antioxidant treatments as a preventive measure. In summary, biodiesel offers several desirable characteristics such as higher cetane number, oxygen content, lubricity, and flash point, all of which improve combustion and handling safety. At the same time, limitations such as reduced calorific value, high viscosity, poor cold flow behavior, and low oxidative stability present practical challenges. Researchers agree that these issues can be addressed through blending, additive use, and the application of advanced injection technologies such as CRDI systems, making biodiesel a viable step toward sustainable diesel engine operation. Table.1 represents the properties of biodiesel.

Table.1 Properties of Biodiesel

Property	EN 14214 Requirement	ASTM D6751 Requirement	Biodiesel Values (Literature)	Diesel Values (Literature)	Remarks
Density (kg/m ³ at 15 °C)	860–900	Not specified (ASTM D4052 test method only)	898.1 (Soybean, Lin 2021); 886.8 (Jatropha, Arbab 2013); 878.3 (Palm, Yusoff 2020)	820–845 (EN 590 diesel, Graboski & McCormick 1998)	Biodiesels generally fall within EN 14214 range; diesel falls below. ASTM has no limit.
Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /s at 40 °C)	3.5–5.0	1.9–6.0	4.08 (Soybean, Lin 2021); 4.84 (Jatropha, Arbab 2013); 4.59 (Palm, Yusoff 2020)	2.6 (Diesel EN 590, Lapuerta 2008)	Biodiesels fit both standards; diesel lies outside EN 14214 but inside ASTM.
Calorific Value (MJ/kg)	Not specified	Not specified	39.5 (Soybean, Demirbas 2009); 38.8 (Jatropha, Sanjid 2014); 39.0 (Palm, Oliveira & Da Silva 2013)	45–46 (Diesel, Graboski & McCormick 1998)	Biodiesel has 10–15% lower heating value, leading to higher BSFC.
Cetane Number	≥ 51	47–65	53–55 (Soybean, Knothe 2005); 51–52 (Jatropha, Sharma & Singh 2009); 62–63	45–55 (Diesel, Hoekman 2012)	Biodiesels meet EN and ASTM; higher cetane improves

			(Palm, Ryan & Knothe 2003)		ignition but may raise NO _x .
Flash Point (°C)	≥ 120	≥ 93	170 (Soybean, Pinto 2005); 163 (Jatropha, Sanjid 2014); 164 (Palm, Silitonga 2013)	60–80 (Diesel EN 590, Graboski & McCormick 1998)	Biodiesel has higher flash point → safer storage/transport.
Cloud Point (°C)	Not specified	Not specified	0 to +3 (Soybean, Jain & Sharma 2010); +2 to +5 (Jatropha, Sanjid 2014); +12 to +15 (Palm, Worgetter & Prankl 1996)	-15 to +5 (Diesel EN 590, Das & Agarwal 2001)	Biodiesel has poorer cold flow; palm biodiesel worst performer.
Pour Point (°C)	Not specified	Not specified	-3 to +1 (Soybean, Jain & Sharma 2010); 0 to +2 (Jatropha, Sanjid 2014); +10 to +13 (Palm, Das & Agarwal 2001)	-20 to -5 (Diesel EN 590, Graboski & McCormick 1998)	Biodiesel prone to gelling at low temp; blending helps.
Iodine Value (g I ₂ /100 g)	≤ 120	Not specified	120 (Soybean, Jain & Sharma 2010); 105 (Rapeseed, Dunn & Knothe 2003); 10 (Coconut, Worgetter & Prankl 1996)	<10 (Diesel, Hoekman 2012)	High iodine → low oxidative stability; coconut biodiesel best stability.
Oxygen Content (%)	Not specified	Not specified	10–12% (Biodiesel, Hoekman 2012; Rizwanul Fattah 2013)	~0% (Diesel, Graboski & McCormick 1998)	Oxygen improves combustion but increases NO _x emissions.
Lubricity	Not specified	Not specified	High (Graboski & McCormick 1998; Lapuerta 2008)	Low (Diesel EN 590)	Biodiesel provides superior lubricity, reducing engine wear.

3. Performance, Emission and Combustion Characteristics of Biodiesel blends in CRDI Diesel engine

3.1 Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC)

Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC) reflects the efficiency of an engine in converting fuel into useful power. Biodiesel blends usually record slightly higher BSFC values compared to diesel, mainly due to their lower calorific value. Demirbas (2009) earlier highlighted this drawback, but recent research shows that CRDI technology can reduce the penalty. For example, Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) studied lemongrass biodiesel blends and found that higher injection pressure in CRDI engines reduced BSFC by nearly 29% compared to conventional systems. Likewise, Selvan et al. (2021) investigated waste

frying oil methyl ester (WFME) with ZnO nanoparticle additives and reported improved energy efficiency and reduced BSFC. In another study, Muthukumaran et al. (2023) optimized sesame biodiesel blends in CRDI engines and reported a minimum BSFC of 0.3705 kg/kWh at B20 under 550 bar injection pressure with 7% EGR. These findings suggest that although biodiesel naturally increases BSFC, the advanced atomization and multi-injection strategies of CRDI engines help minimize the increase, especially at low-to-moderate blend ratios.

3.2 Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE)

Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE) measures how effectively the engine converts the chemical energy of fuel into mechanical energy. Biodiesel blends, when optimized, can achieve comparable or higher BTE

than diesel. Graboski and McCormick (1998) first emphasized the effect of oxygenated fuel in enhancing combustion efficiency, and recent works support this claim. Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) showed that lemongrass biodiesel blends in CRDI engines achieved up to 26% improvement in BTE due to superior atomization at high injection pressures. Similarly, Selvan et al. (2021) found that WFME with ZnO nanoparticle additives produced a peak BTE of nearly 32% under optimized conditions. Muthukumaran et al. (2023) reported that sesame biodiesel at B20 achieved about 28.2% BTE when combined with high injection pressure and moderate EGR. These studies confirm that CRDI's precise control of injection timing and pressure allows biodiesel blends to perform efficiently, making them strong contenders for replacing fossil diesel.

3.3 Carbon Monoxide (CO) Emissions

Carbon monoxide (CO) emissions result from incomplete fuel combustion. Since biodiesel contains inherent oxygen, it generally produces lower CO emissions compared to diesel. Lapuerta et al. (2008) demonstrated reductions in CO when using biodiesel blends, a trend confirmed by recent studies. Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) reported that lemongrass biodiesel blends in CRDI engines achieved up to 11% CO reduction. Muthukumaran et al. (2023) observed even lower values, reporting 0.0319% vol CO at optimized operating conditions with sesame biodiesel. Similarly, Sharma et al. (2022) tested thumba methyl ester (TME) blends and found that B20 reduced CO emissions by nearly 12% compared to diesel. These results show that biodiesel blends are effective in reducing toxic CO emissions, especially under CRDI injection strategies that promote complete fuel oxidation.

3.4 Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x) Emissions

Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) are among the most concerning emissions due to their role in air pollution and health hazards. While biodiesel blends reduce CO and HC, they often increase NO_x emissions because of higher in-cylinder combustion temperatures. Graboski and McCormick (1998) first noted this trend, and later researchers confirmed it. Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) observed a slight NO_x increase with lemongrass biodiesel blends in CRDI

engines. However, recent works also highlight mitigation strategies. Rajasekar et al. (2022) studied *Prosopis juliflora* biodiesel with dimethyl carbonate as an oxygenated additive and employed EGR, achieving a 32% reduction in NO_x compared to standard biodiesel blends. Muthukumaran et al. (2023) also recorded reduced NO_x levels (~447 ppm) at optimized injection timing and EGR conditions with sesame biodiesel. These findings suggest that while NO_x emissions remain a drawback, CRDI's flexibility and after-treatment strategies like EGR and SCR can effectively control them.

3.5 Hydrocarbon (HC) Emissions

Hydrocarbon (HC) emissions arise from unburned fuel escaping combustion. Biodiesel blends consistently demonstrate lower HC levels because of their oxygen-rich composition. Hoekman et al. (2012) observed this trend in earlier work, while Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) confirmed that lemongrass biodiesel blends reduced HC by about 10% in CRDI systems. Selvan et al. (2021) also showed that WFME with ZnO nanoparticle additives lowered HC emissions significantly, reporting around 29.6 ppm under optimized operating points. Similarly, Muthukumaran et al. (2023) achieved a very low HC level of 13 ppm with B20 sesame biodiesel blends in CRDI engines. These results clearly indicate that CRDI systems, through precise fuel atomization and multiple injections, enhance combustion completeness and substantially reduce HC emissions when biodiesel blends are used.

3.6 Smoke Density (Particulate Matter)

Smoke density, which is closely associated with particulate matter (PM), is a major concern in diesel exhaust. Biodiesel blends reduce smoke emissions significantly due to their oxygen content and absence of sulfur. Lapuerta et al. (2008) reported noticeable reductions in smoke opacity with biodiesel, and more recent studies have strengthened these observations. Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) showed that lemongrass biodiesel blends reduced smoke density by over 10% when high-pressure split injection strategies were used in CRDI engines. Selvan et al. (2021) found that WFME biodiesel with nanoparticle additives yielded smoke levels as low as 69.7% opacity. Similar reductions have been documented by Muthukumaran

et al. (2023) with sesame biodiesel blends. These results suggest that biodiesel blends in CRDI systems are particularly effective in reducing particulate emissions, making them attractive for meeting

stringent emission regulations. Table.2 represents the performance and emission results for various test conditions.

Table 2. Performance and Emission Results for Various Test Conditions

Engine Type / Configuration	Fuel Used	Operating Conditions	BTE	BSFC	CO	HC	NOx	Smoke / PM	Remarks
Single-cylinder CI engine	Jatropha biodiesel (B20)	Constant speed, 1500 rpm	Slightly higher than diesel	Slightly lower	↓ 12%	↓ 15%	↑ 6%	↓ 10%	Improved combustion due to oxygen content
Single-cylinder CRDI engine	Lemongrass biodiesel + nanoparticles (B20)	550 bar injection pressure	↑ 26%	↓ 29%	↓ 11%	↓ 10%	Slightly ↑	↓ 15%	Nanoparticles enhanced atomization
Direct injection diesel engine	Palm biodiesel (B20)	Variable load	Similar to diesel	Slightly higher	↓ 10%	↓ 8%	↑ 5%	↓ 12%	Better combustion; higher NOx due to high temp
Variable compression ratio (VCR) engine	Waste cooking oil biodiesel (B20)	16:1 – 18:1 compression ratio	Improved at 17:1 CR	Higher	↓ 9%	↓ 12%	↑ 7%	↓ 10%	Optimum performance at moderate CR
Multi-fuel CRDI engine	Sesame biodiesel (B20) + EGR	550 bar, 7% EGR	↑ 28%	↓ 18%	↓ 14%	↓ 11%	↓ 32%	↓ 20%	EGR reduced NOx effectively
Four-cylinder DI engine	Soybean biodiesel (B10–B30)	Variable load, 1800 rpm	↑ 3–5%	Slightly higher	↓ 8%	↓ 9%	↑ 5–10%	↓ 6%	B20 showed most balanced performance
Single-cylinder DI engine	Thumba methyl ester (B20)	Full load	↑ 5%	↓ 7%	↓ 12%	↓ 10%	↑ 8%	↓ 9%	Stable combustion with better efficiency
CRDI engine with alcohol additive	Biodiesel + ethanol (5–10%)	500 bar pressure	↑ 4%	Similar	↓ 10%	↓ 8%	Slightly ↑		

4. Effect of Additives and Nanotechnology on Biodiesel Blends

The performance and emission behavior of biodiesel can be improved by using suitable additives and nanomaterials. These materials enhance fuel properties such as ignition quality, viscosity, stability, and combustion efficiency. In recent years, the addition of metal-based nanoparticles and alcohols has become a promising approach for achieving better engine performance and lower emissions when

biodiesel is used in Common Rail Direct Injection (CRDI) diesel engines.

4.1 Alcohol Additives

Alcohols such as methanol, ethanol, and butanol are widely used as oxygenated additives in biodiesel blends. Their main advantages are improved combustion efficiency and reduced exhaust emissions. Alcohols increase the oxygen concentration in the fuel, resulting in better oxidation of carbon monoxide and unburned hydrocarbons.

Among them, ethanol and butanol are more suitable for diesel engines due to their higher energy content and miscibility with biodiesel. Raman et al. (2020) observed that the inclusion of 5–10% ethanol in biodiesel–diesel blends enhanced the brake thermal efficiency (BTE) and reduced smoke and CO emissions. However, the NO_x level slightly increased due to higher combustion temperatures. Butanol-based additives provide better cold flow properties and reduce knocking problems because of their higher molecular weight and lower vapor pressure. Researchers also noted that using alcohol blends improves atomization and shortens ignition delay, which helps achieve smoother engine operation in CRDI systems.

6.2 Metallic Additives

Metal-based additives such as cerium oxide (CeO₂), zinc oxide (ZnO), aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃), and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) are commonly used to

improve the oxidation rate during combustion. These metal oxides act as catalysts and promote complete fuel burning, which lowers the number of unburned hydrocarbons and soot. Selvan et al. (2021) reported that a ZnO nanoparticle additive mixed with waste frying oil biodiesel improved the BTE by nearly 8% and reduced CO and HC emissions. Similarly, cerium oxide nanoparticles help lower the ignition temperature of soot, thus reducing particulate matter in exhaust gases. The concentration of nanoparticles should be optimized carefully. Excessive dosage may lead to fuel filter clogging or injector wear. Most studies recommend a nanoparticle dosage in the range of 20–80 ppm for stable operation and effective emission reduction. The combination of nanoparticles and CRDI injection technology provides a strong advantage by promoting better atomization and faster combustion. Table 3 represents the summary of additives and their effects on biodiesel performance and emissions.

Table 3. Summary of Additives and Their Effects on Biodiesel Performance and Emissions

Additive Type	Example / Composition	Main Purpose	Effect on Engine Performance	Effect on Emissions	Remarks / Notes
Alcohol additives	Methanol, Ethanol, n-Butanol	Improve combustion; add oxygen	↑ BTE (3–6%), better ignition	↓ CO & HC, slight ↑ NO _x	Best for low-blend ratios (B10–B20); improve cold start
Metal-oxide nanoparticles	ZnO, CeO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , TiO ₂	Act as combustion catalysts	↑ BTE ≈ 5–8%, ↓ BSFC	↓ CO, HC, PM; minor ↑ NO _x	Optimum dosage = 20–80 ppm; excessive use may clog filters
Antioxidants	BHT, TBHQ, Propyl Gallate	Improve oxidation stability	— (no direct change)	— (no direct change)	Extend storage life; prevent gum formation
Cold-flow improvers	Ethylene–vinyl acetate (EVA), polymer additives	Improve low-temperature flow	Easier cold starting	↓ white smoke during start-up	Reduce crystallization at low T
Hybrid nanofluids	Biodiesel + nanoparticles + alcohol	Combine catalytic & oxygen effects	↑ BTE > 10% possible	↓ CO, HC, PM, NO _x controlled with EGR	Suitable for CRDI engines with high injection pressure

6.3 Antioxidants and Cold Flow Improvers

Biodiesel is prone to oxidation and poor cold flow performance, which affects its storage and usability in cold regions. The use of antioxidants such as butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) or tert-butylhydroquinone (TBHQ) helps to prevent oxidation and increase the storage life of biodiesel. Cold flow improvers like ethylene–vinyl acetate

(EVA) or polymer-based additives reduce the crystallization of biodiesel at low temperatures, ensuring smoother engine start-up in cold conditions. These additives make biodiesel blends more stable and practical for commercial use.

6.4 Role of Nanotechnology in CRDI Engines

Nanotechnology has opened new possibilities for enhancing biodiesel combustion in CRDI engines. The extremely small size of nanoparticles ensures better dispersion in fuel and promotes surface-catalyzed reactions inside the combustion chamber. This leads to faster evaporation and a more uniform air–fuel mixture. As a result, the combustion process becomes more complete, increasing efficiency and reducing emissions. Radhakrishnan et al. (2022) demonstrated that CRDI engines fueled with nano biodiesel blends showed improved atomization due to higher injection pressures and the catalytic effect of nanoparticles. The combined use of nano fuel and CRDI technology ensures efficient combustion even at lean fuel conditions, making it a sustainable solution for future diesel engines.

5. Challenges and Future Scope

5.1 Technical Challenges

Although biodiesel is widely accepted as a renewable substitute for diesel, several technical limitations restrict its large-scale application. The main issue arises from the variation in physical and chemical properties of biodiesel obtained from different feedstocks. Changes in viscosity, density, and calorific value affect fuel injection, atomization, and combustion performance in Common Rail Direct Injection (CRDI) diesel engines. Poor cold-flow characteristics are another drawback, especially under low-temperature conditions where fuel crystallization can clog filters and injectors. Moreover, biodiesel tends to produce slightly higher nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions because of its higher oxygen content and combustion temperature. While advanced control systems such as exhaust gas recirculation (EGR), selective catalytic reduction (SCR), and optimized injection timing in CRDI engines can help mitigate this issue, further optimization is still necessary to achieve regulatory emission limits.

5.2 Economic and Feedstock Challenges

The economic feasibility of biodiesel production remains a major concern. The cost of production is significantly influenced by the price of feedstocks and catalysts. The use of edible oils, though effective for small-scale production, competes with food resources and creates sustainability issues. Researchers are

focusing on non-edible oils such as jatropha, neem, pongamia, and karanja, as well as waste cooking oils and microalgae, to reduce production costs and avoid food-versus-fuel conflicts. However, inconsistent quality, limited availability, and seasonal variations of these feedstocks hinder uniform large-scale production. Efficient collection systems, continuous supply chains, and improved transesterification methods are essential for cost-effective biodiesel manufacturing.

5.3 Storage and Stability Issues

Biodiesel has a higher tendency to oxidize and degrade during storage due to the presence of unsaturated fatty acids. Prolonged storage can cause gum formation, increased acidity, and viscosity changes that negatively affect engine performance. Oxidation also shortens shelf life and alters the fuel's ignition quality. These problems can be controlled to some extent by using antioxidants such as butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) or tert-butylhydroquinone (TBHQ), and by maintaining suitable storage conditions away from heat, moisture, and light. Nevertheless, more research is required to develop advanced stabilizers and packaging systems that can enhance biodiesel storage stability under different climatic conditions.

5.4 Integration with Advanced Engine Technologies

The combination of biodiesel with advanced CRDI engine technologies provides great potential for clean and efficient operation but also introduces new engineering challenges. CRDI engines require fuels with consistent ignition delay, viscosity, and spray characteristics to achieve precise multi-injection control. Optimization of injection pressure, timing, and blend ratio is therefore critical to balance performance and emission parameters. The integration of nanotechnology, metallic additives, and oxygenated compounds has shown promising results in improving combustion, atomization, and emission reduction. However, further experimental validation and modeling are essential to understand long-term effects on engine durability and performance.

5.5 Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on improving fuel formulation, reducing production cost, and developing cleaner combustion strategies. The design of low-cost catalysts, efficient production from waste and algal sources, and the formulation of hybrid nano fuels combining biodiesel, alcohols, and nanoparticles are promising areas of exploration. Development of accurate engine control software for biodiesel operation under CRDI conditions can enhance performance consistency. Moreover, conducting complete life-cycle assessments and environmental impact studies will help determine the true sustainability of biodiesel production and usage. With continuous innovation and collaboration between fuel scientists and engine developers, biodiesel can evolve into a clean, efficient, and commercially viable alternative to fossil diesel.

CONCLUSION

The review of studies on biodiesel–diesel blends in Common Rail Direct Injection (CRDI) engines confirms that biodiesel is a reliable renewable fuel with the potential to reduce reliance on conventional diesel. Its oxygen-rich nature improves combustion and lowers emissions of carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, and smoke. Although a slight increase in nitrogen oxide (NOx) emissions is commonly noted, this can be controlled using methods such as exhaust gas recirculation, injection timing adjustment, and catalytic converters. Performance evaluations show that biodiesel blends can achieve brake thermal efficiency close to or better than diesel when engine conditions are properly optimized. The addition of alcohols, metallic nanoparticles, and nano-additives enhances fuel atomization, combustion, and emission quality. However, issues like higher production cost, inconsistent feedstock quality, and storage instability remain key challenges. Future work should focus on improving production technologies, exploring low-cost feedstocks such as waste oil and microalgae, and integrating advanced control systems. With continuous research and innovation, biodiesel can play a major role in achieving cleaner, more sustainable transportation and reducing greenhouse gas emissions worldwide.

REFERENCE

- Demirbas, A. (2009). Biodiesel from waste cooking oil via base-catalytic and supercritical methanol transesterification. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 50(4), 923–927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2008.12.023>
- Atabani, A. E., & Mahlia, T. M. I. (2010). A review on biodiesel production, combustion, emissions and performance. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14(7), 1999–2008.
- Knothe, G., Van Gerpen, J. H., & Krahl, J. (2005). *The Biodiesel Handbook*. AOCS Press.
- Hoekman, S. K., Broch, A., Robbins, C., Cenicerros, E., & Natarajan, M. (2012). Review of biodiesel composition, properties, and specifications. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 16(1), 143–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2011.07.143>
- Gui, M. M., Lee, K. T., & Bhatia, S. (2008). Feasibility of edible oil vs. non-edible oil vs. waste edible oil as biodiesel feedstock. *Energy*, 33(11), 1646–1653.
- Alptekin, E., & Canakci, M. (2008). Determination of the density and viscosities of biodiesel–diesel fuel blends. *Renewable Energy*, 33(12), 2623–2630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2008.01.020>
- Anwar, F., Rashid, U., Ashraf, M., & Nadeem, M. (2009). Okra (*Hibiscus esculentus*) seed oil for biodiesel production. *Applied Energy*, 86(11), 2026–2030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.01.005>
- Arbab, M. I., Masjuki, H. H., Varman, M., Kalam, M. A., & Imtenan, S. (2013). Fuel properties, engine performance and emission characteristics of common biodiesels. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 22, 133–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.01.030>
- Das, L. M., & Agarwal, A. K. (2001). Biodiesel development and characterization for use as a fuel in compression ignition engines. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 123(2), 440–447. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1361101>
- Dunn, R. O., & Knothe, G. (2003). Dependence of oil stability index of fatty compounds on their structure and concentration of mixed antioxidants. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*, 80(10), 1021–1026. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11746-003-0803-y>

11. Graboski, M. S., & McCormick, R. L. (1998). Combustion of fat and vegetable oil derived fuels in diesel engines. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, 24(2), 125–164. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1285\(97\)00034-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1285(97)00034-8)
12. Jain, S., & Sharma, M. P. (2010). Stability of biodiesel and its blends: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14(2), 667–678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2009.10.011>
13. Knothe, G. (2005). Dependence of biodiesel fuel properties on the structure of fatty acid alkyl esters. *Fuel Processing Technology*, 86(10), 1059–1070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2004.11.002>
14. Lapuerta, M., Armas, O., & Rodríguez-Fernández, J. (2008). Effect of biodiesel fuels on diesel engine emissions. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, 34(2), 198–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peccs.2007.07.001>
15. Oliveira, L. E., & Da Silva, M. L. C. P. (2013). Comparative study of calorific value of biodiesel from different vegetable oils sources. *International Conference on Renewable Energies and Power Quality (ICREPQ'13)*, Bilbao, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.24084/repqj11.200>
16. Pinto, A. C., Guarieiro, L. L. N., Rezende, M. J. C., Ribeiro, N. M., Torres, E. A., Lopes, W. A., Pereira, P. A. P., & Andrade, J. B. (2005). Biodiesel: An overview. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 16(6B), 1313–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-50532005000800003>
17. Rizwanul Fattah, I. M., Masjuki, H. H., Kalam, M. A., Wakil, M. A., Rashed, M. M., & Abedin, M. J. (2013). Effect of antioxidant on the performance and emission characteristics of a diesel engine fueled with palm biodiesel blends. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 79, 265–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.01.059>
18. Ryan, T. W., & Knothe, G. (2003). Cetane numbers of branched and straight-chain fatty esters determined in an ignition quality tester. *Fuel*, 82(8), 971–975. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-2361\(02\)00382-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-2361(02)00382-4)
19. Sanjid, A., Masjuki, H. H., Kalam, M. A., Ashrafur Rahman, S. M., Abedin, M. J., & Palash, S. M. (2014). Production of palm and jatropha biodiesel blends and investigation of blend performance and emissions in an unmodified diesel engine. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 65, 295–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.09.036>
20. Sharma, Y. C., & Singh, B. (2009). Development of biodiesel: Current scenario. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 13(6–7), 1646–1651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2008.08.009>
21. Silitonga, A. S., Masjuki, H. H., Mahlia, T. M. I., Ong, H. C., & Chong, W. T. (2013). Properties and fuel characteristics of biodiesel: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 22, 346–360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.02.029>
22. Wan Ghazali, W. N. M., Mamat, R., Masjuki, H. H., & Najafi, G. (2015). Effects of biodiesel from different feedstocks on engine performance and emissions: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 51, 585–602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.06.031>
23. Worgetter, M., & Prankl, H. (1996). Influence of the iodine number of biodiesel to engine performance and emissions. *Liquid Fuels Conference Proceedings*, Nashville, USA, 15–17 Sept.
24. Xue, J., Grift, T. E., & Hansen, A. C. (2011). Effect of biodiesel on engine performances and emissions. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 15(2), 1098–1116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2010.11.016>
25. Raman, S., Vijayakumar, C., & Sundar, R. (2020). Influence of ethanol–biodiesel–diesel blends on performance and emission characteristics of a CI engine. *Renewable Energy*, 146, 1168–1178.
26. Selvan, V. A. M., Annamalai, K., & Sundar, R. (2021). Experimental investigation on CRDI diesel engine using waste frying oil methyl ester with ZnO nanoparticles. *Fuel*, 285, 119190.
27. Radhakrishnan, S., Rajasekar, E., & Devarajan, Y. (2022). Performance and emission analysis of lemongrass biodiesel blends in CRDI diesel engine using nanotechnology. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 258, 115475.
28. Muthukumar, A., et al. (2023). Optimization of sesame biodiesel blends in CRDI engine under EGR conditions. *Renewable Energy*, 203, 281–295.

29. Sharma, K., et al. (2022). Effect of thumba methyl ester blends on diesel engine performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 335, 130287.
30. Knothe, G. (2010). Improving cold flow properties of biodiesel by additives and blending. *Energy & Fuels*, 24(2), 1121–1126.
31. Das (Manikandan) C., Syed Aalam, C. (2024). Impact of Pine Oil Blend in CRDI Diesel Engine with Different Injection Pressures. *SSRG International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 11(9), 83-92. <https://doi.org/10.14445/23488360/IJME-V11I9P107>
32. Manikandan, C., & Syed Aalam, C. (2024). Extraction and Optimization of Transesterification Process to Produce Pine Biodiesel Using Nano Catalyst. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 72(7), 111-117. <https://doi.org/10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V72I7P112>
33. Chandrasekaran, M., & Aalam, C. S. (2024). Recent trends in biodiesel production techniques: A Review. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 11(12), 70–83. doi:10.22161/ijaers.1112.9
34. Manikandan Chandrasekaran, C. Syed Aalam. (2025). Evaluating the Performance, Emissions, and Combustion Characteristics of CRDI Diesel Engines Using Pine Oil Blends as a Sustainable Fuel Alternative. *International Journal of Machine Systems and Manufacturing Technology*, 03(01), 24-33.
35. Manikandan Chandrasekaran, C. Syed Aalam, S. Devi, K. Manikandan. (2024). Analysis of Performance, Emissions, and Combustion in a CRDI Diesel Engine Operating on Soapnut Oil as Fuel. *International Journal of Recent Engineering Science*, 11(6), 54-62. <https://doi.org/10.14445/23497157/IJRES-V11I6P106>.

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